

Machine Learning-Based Semantic Entity Alignment for Multi-Source Data: a Systematic Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

It has become more common to store data about real-world entities, where this data is often distributed across multiple data sources. Entity alignment helps with merging and managing such data by identifying and linking similar entities stored in each of the data sources. Many machine learning-based semantic entity alignment approaches have been proposed by the recent studies in the field. The goal of this systematic literature review is to give an overview of the most recent studies that address entity alignment, as well as to answer some of the research questions that are formulated based on the current research trends in this field. In this study we investigate and summarize two novel methods to compute semantic similarity, two metrics used to measure the quality of semantic similarity between knowledge base entities, and seven state-of-the-art ML-based semantic entity alignment approaches. We also investigate recent studies that touch upon user experience, privacy preservation, decentralized environment and other properties related to entity alignment. We conclude this study with an overview of the main findings presented in a table and graphic forms. We also present a taxonomy of results that can be used by other researchers in this field to get a clear overview of the most recent ML-based semantic entity alignment methods.

KEYWORDS

Systematic Literature Review, Machine Learning, Entity Alignment, Semantic Similarity, Active Learning, Knowledge Graph

1 INTRODUCTION

Driven by the Linked Open Data (LOD) [7] and knowledge graph [33] initiatives, it is becoming increasingly more common to store and manage data about real-world entities in a number of large, often distributed, databases or data lakes [52]. Such architectures can quickly introduce many problems with information about the same real-world entity being stored multiple times in the same data source or parts of the data being distributed across multiple sources. Entity alignment aims to solve these problems by linking entities that denote the same object in the real-world and in turn to facilitate information integration and retrieval. More concrete examples that make use of entity alignment approaches include:

- (1) merging two databases or cleaning a database, where it is important to determine when two tuple records are referring to the same real-world object (deduplication and data integration).
- (2) natural language processing when the task is to determine which noun phrases refer to the same underlying entity (coreference resolution)

- (3) computer vision, where two regions in different images refer to the same object (the correspondence problem)

In addition, deduplication is important for removing redundancy and for accurate data analysis, while in information integration determining approximate joins is important for consolidating information from multiple sources.

Entity alignment of knowledge graphs is enabled by the development of the assisting tools, such as graph database management systems (graph DBMS). Some of the most famous graph DBMS are: Neo4j, DGraph, Amazon Neptune, Azure Cosmos DB, IBM Graph, Apache Giraph, Oracle Spatial & Graph and more. These DBMS are capable of storing large amounts of data in the form of nodes and edges, where nodes represent real-world entities being stored and their properties, and edges represent the relationships between these entities. In their paper Guia et al. [26] describe a few advantages of graph DBMS, which include an optimized information search, an intuitive form of information representation, agile development, high performance and more. Such databases are capable of not only storing the information about the entity, but also reflecting the semantic meaning of those entities through labels, properties, neighbors, types of relationships, class hierarchy, data schema, etc.

An important step of entity alignment is computing similarity between entities from two or more knowledge graphs. According to Wan et al. [74] it can be highly beneficial to make use of the semantic information that comes in form of an ontology, which is either derived from the underlying data or comes from an external source. There exist a number of other methods that do not makes use of the semantic information or external ontologies when computing similarity between two entities, however the focus of this paper is to investigate semantic matching models only. The benefit of using semantic models is that it allows us to have a better understanding of entities before finding existing matches. The matching is based on a numeric score, usually between 0 and 100, that quantifies the similarity of entities of different sources [53]. When semantic models are used to measure similarity, it is usually based on a few specific relationships (e.g *is-a*, *same-as*, *also-known-as*, etc.) found in the underlying taxonomy or ontology in which the concepts reside. An example of semantically similar vs. semantically different entities is shown in Figure 1. Here the task is to find out similarity of an entity called "New Amsterdam" and two other entities. If we were to use a string-based similarity for this task, the entity "New Amsterdam" would have a low similarity score with the entity "New York City", but a high similarity score with an entity "Amsterdam". In this case this is an example of a misalignment, since "New Amsterdam" and "Amsterdam" refer to two different real-world entities. However, when using a semantic matching model to compute similarity we can match these entities correctly,

since it can make use of an external ontology, like Wikidata [73]. When browsing Wikidata for an entity called "New Amsterdam" we see that it is related to "New York City" with a *followed-by* relation and to "Amsterdam" with a *named-after* relation. When computing similarity of these entities, "New York City" will produce a high similarity score, because "New Amsterdam" is a reference to the exact same real-world entity that uses a different (older) name. Of course, this specific example is one of many examples that shows the importance of semantic knowledge when matching data entities.

Figure 1: An example of semantically similar vs. semantically different entities.

Such examples of external semantic information become very beneficial when used in combination with a machine learning model to perform entity alignment. One of the most prominent examples is that after training a machine learning model to compute semantic similarity, this model can be reused in the future with the new data or other datasets. Additionally, there has been many improvements in the area of transfer learning [31] and active learning [50] [62], which is useful to compute semantic similarity of the domain-specific knowledge, where machine learning can outperform NLP or any other approach due to its ability to identify complex patterns that can give valuable insights about the data. The advantages of these models are that they take the semantics into account during training and therefore potentially reduce the search space and that they can exploit dependencies between classes during training and prediction. The main disadvantage is the increased complexity of these classifiers [64].

Given new advancements in the area of entity alignment this study presents a systematic literature review of the recent research studies to analyze initiatives that enable entity alignment by integrating machine learning approaches together with semantic information about real-world entities. The incentive behind this

literature review is mainly based on the literature gaps that are present in the current state of entity alignment, as well as our personal interest in this area. Finally, it is important to mention that this literature study will be used as a starting point of a larger project, which aims at (1) implementing and comparing entity alignment techniques on a domain-specific data that consists of IT assets of a large banking company, whose data is distributed across multiple data sources; (2) making best use of the results of entity alignment to give recommendations to the users with regard to their specific information needs.

The contributions of this literature study are the following: (1) an abstract categorization of the ML-based semantic entity alignment models, (2) an entity alignment research focused on user experience, privacy preservation and decentralization, (3) identification of current research gaps and future research directions in the area of semantic entity alignment, (4) identification of different state-of-the-art approaches and their features, and (5) an abstracted view of different state-of-the-art approaches and the key steps they take for entity alignment.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of the most recent work related to entity alignment. Section 3 describes the methodology of this study, including a list of research questions, the rationale, as well as phases of the search process. Section 4 discusses the results of the data extraction carried in this paper. Section 5 provides a discussion of the results that are structured in a form of a taxonomy. Section 6 gives an overview of different threats to validity of this study. Section 7 concludes the study and gives potential implications and directions for the future work.

2 RELATED WORK

In the existing literature there are many same/similar concepts related to entity alignment, such as data matching, entity resolution, data mapping, record linkage, link discovery, reference reconciliation, merge-purge and more. There is a lot of interesting research related to semantic text similarity, semantic machine learning, semantic search engines and Semantic Web data processing that briefly touch upon semantic entity alignment, but do not specifically focus on this subject. Some of these papers are also included in this literature study, as long as it does not deviate the main goal of this research.

One of the most recent surveys was done by Chandrasekaran and Mago [11], where they discuss the evolution of computing semantic similarity, but also provide a detailed overview of the advantages, and disadvantages of different semantic similarity methods. According to their research knowledge-based semantic similarity use the meaning of text, however, they fall short when used across different domains and languages. On the contrary to the knowledge based methods, corpus-based methods use statistics at its core and perform well with cross-lingual data, but actual meaning of the text is then lost. Another group of semantic similarity methods use deep neural networks, which perform much better than other methods, but they lack interpretability and also require high computational resources. Finally, there is a variety of hybrid methods that aim at exploiting the benefits of different methods by combining them, while also making their shortcomings less noticeable. The survey

makes it clear that choosing one best model from all the possible methods is difficult, yet they indicate that most recent hybrid methods have shown promising results and exhibiting superiority over other independent models. While the authors do mention the lack of work on computational efficiency and performance as the future research directions, they do not touch on specific properties of semantic similarity methods, e.g. scalability, privacy concerns, the use in distributed environment, user experience and potential applications.

Another substantial study on semantic similarity measures and semantic machine learning models has been done by Traverso Ribón [61]. In his dissertation Traverso Ribón focuses on studying the value of using semantics in node similarity measures and how these semantic similarity measures can enhance the quality of knowledge graphs. The motivation of his work comes from the raising amount of semantically described data and the existence of many similarity measures that only use a single aspect of data to compute semantic similarity. Such measures achieve better, but still similar performance as a simple Jaccard similarity measure [49]. Rather than using a single aspect of the underlying data this work proves that combining multiple aspects offered by different semantic descriptions can become much more beneficial when computing semantic similarity. Another contribution of this study is that it proves the benefit of considering semantics in the computations of similarity. Namely, the semantics of data provides most benefit to relation discovery in knowledge graphs and integration of Linked Data datasets. The quality of the semantic descriptions plays an important role on how effective the semantics are when used to compute similarity. Despite the fact that this study is quite elaborate, it has been conducted in 2017 which is the reason why it fails to address many newer developments in the area of semantic similarity or entity alignment. Moreover, the proposed methods of enhancement of knowledge graphs with semantics do not address specific problems related to privacy, distributed computing environments and other more recent research areas.

A brief study by Sitikhu et al. [65] mainly focuses on maximizing human interpretability of semantic similarity of short texts. In their study they analyze three different approaches for computing the semantic similarity between short news articles. The approaches that were used are cosine similarity with tf-idf vectors, cosine similarity with Word2vec vectors and soft cosine similarity with Word2vec vectors, where all of them has shown promising results. When comparing the newsgroup of a text article and its corresponding most similar article, machine learning-based cosine with tf-idf feature vectors has the highest accuracy during the cross-validation of the results. The output of the cosine with tf-idf semantic similarity, which consists of the most similar documents given by the method are easy to interpret, which makes it eligible to use for information retrieval. Interestingly, Sitikhu et al. show that by using the Doc2vec model instead of the Word2Vec model, it is possible to increase the accuracy of the other two models. Since the focus of this study is quite narrow, it does not provide the overview of all most recent research advancements in computing semantic similarity, only the ones that specifically address human interpretability.

In their study Papadakis et al.[52] provide a broad literature coverage which serves as a basis for designing JedAI, an Entity

Resolution tool that can also be used as a library of the main established techniques in the literature. In their research Papadakis et al. cover both application in academic and commercial scenarios to produce an application that incorporates methods that support four different end-to-end Entity Resolution workflows. This application integrates the following state-of-the-art ER techniques: budget-agnostic based on batch, schema-agnostic based on blocks and schema-based relying on similarity joins. As part of JedAI Papadakis et al. also offer the ability to build and benchmark millions of ER pipelines, applications to structured and semi-structured data, running on stand-alone and cluster computers through parallel implementation and adaption to budget-aware ER. However, even though the methods incorporated in JedAI perform well in terms of scalability, they highly rely on syntax of data and do not yet integrate semantics into any of its workflows, which arguably makes it perform poorly with certain domain-specific types of data.

Reynoso and Divan[60] present a systematic mapping study, that addresses semantic similarity of entities and the reuse of the knowledge and previous experiences when a new entity has either none or little evidence, but is similar to another entity. Thus, when designing a system focused on decision making, the reuse of the knowledge and previous experiences plays an important role, especially for recommendations provided to the user. The study concludes that the semantic similarity applied to entities under monitoring in the measurement and evaluation projects is a challenge. In the end, the authors suggest a comparative analysis among the strategies, functionalities, and algorithms related to the semantic similarity, however they do not mention the importance of certain semantic matching properties, like privacy preservation, where the reuse of the previous knowledge should not be able to reveal any sensitive information.

The following studies address issues that are also related to semantic entity alignment: schema matching [37, 41], entity resolution [14, 71], Information extraction on Semantic Web [45], Semantic Web ontology tools [77], Semantic Analysis [63], Semantic Segmentation with Deep Learning [27], where the authors integrate and show the added benefit of semantic methods used for specific tasks.

3 STUDY DESIGN

This section describes the methodology that is used to design this literature study. This includes the definition of the research goal, research questions, search queries, inclusion and exclusion criteria, phases of the search process, data extraction method and a section that addresses study replicability.

3.1 Research Goal

This research is designed with the goal of making a comprehensive analysis of the current state-of-the-art ML-based semantic entity alignment methods, as well as metrics used to evaluate these methods. By using this analysis, an investigation can be carried out to compare different methods based on specific properties of models used to perform entity alignment (e.g. user experience, privacy preservation, decentralization and more). Another important part of our goal is to examine current literature gaps and give suggestion for the further research for entity alignment.

3.2 Research Questions

The following research questions have been formulated to gain in-depth insights about the most recent research of machine learning, semantic similarity, entity alignment techniques, as well as some specific characteristics and concepts.

- RQ₁* : How to identify and compute semantic similarity among entities?
- RQ₂* : What are the quality metrics to assess a semantic similarity?
- RQ₃* : What are the state-of-the-art machine learning approaches in semantic entity alignment pipeline?
- RQ₄* : How active learning is used in semantic entity alignment pipeline?
- RQ₅* : How to optimize user experience in semantic entity alignment using machine learning?
- RQ₆* : How does semantic entity alignment work in a decentralized environment?
- RQ₇* : How can data privacy be preserved during the semantic entity alignment?
- RQ₈* : What are the research directions in machine learning-based semantic entity alignment field?

RQ₁ : Various approaches used to compute semantic similarity of real-world entities should be considered. It is also important to investigate the effect of different existing ontologies and vocabularies that describe the meaning of concepts within the domain and the relationships that hold between them. In the presence of such external source of knowledge, it is possible to derive labels describing the semantics of a data entity or even the domain of its origin. [37] Then, a match between two entities is valid when there is a significant overlap between their corresponding labels or, equivalently, they come from the same domain.

RQ₂ : Many quality metrics aim at identifying a unique set of key components that can be used to evaluate the results produced by different methods. Measuring the quality of a similarity model is an important part of its evaluation process. An example of a metric that is used as an alternative to precision and recall is Vaughan [72] criteria, which is used to assess the search systems. Vaughan criteria includes Vaughan's Quality of Result Ranking and Vaughan's Ability to Retrieve Top Ranked Pages. These criteria aim at giving a better reflection of the performance of the search system when compared to other similar systems.

RQ₃ : Analyzing different state-of-the-art entity alignment approaches helps with understanding which factors are essential for its performance. Identifying the state-of-the-art is not an easy task, since the performance of each semantic entity alignment approach highly depends on the usage of different types of external semantic information for the initialization or training/testing sets for the learning model, where different size splits of data can make the results of different approaches incomparable.

RQ₄ : An important feature of an entity alignment model is its ability to retrieve and rank the similarity results accurately. However, setting too high of a threshold of accuracy can result in fewer results retrieved and a negative impact on user experience [4]. Sometimes there is an option to include human experts into the machine learning lifecycle, either during training, to help train the model when

something is unclear, or during the testing to give the feedback to the model and help improve its future performance. The human experts are the people who create, use and/or maintain entities that are stored in the database. Also, the database maintenance team can have quite a lot of insights about the entities and their relationships. The term Active Learning is generally used to refer to a learning problem or system where the learner has some role in determining on what data it will be trained [15].

RQ₅ : Entity alignment produces a list of entities and their similarity scores with other entities as a result. This result can be consumed by either a machine, to perform further data integration or data deduplication for example, or it can be consumed by a user to get a better view of the entities stored in the given data sources. The latter case is where user experience plays an important role and according to Jordan and Mitchell [35] it can be enhanced through the use of machine learning models. The relationship between user experience and machine learning is based on the ability of the machine learning model to learn from large data sets to create personalized experiences for individuals and groups of individuals, thanks to ubiquitous computing. However, these personalized experiences enabled by machine learning are largely based on the context of use, which is an important factor of user experience.

RQ₆ : In comparison to a traditional certain database, a distributed database contains uncertain nodes, which represent a set of possible database instances, called possible worlds, rather than one single world [3]. Some entity alignment methods use machine learning models that are completely distributed and do not depend on the existence of certain nodes. The goal of the distributed entity alignment is to minimize bandwidth usage and reducing processing time of uncertain entities. However, decentralized environments pose other challenges that need to be addressed accordingly when performing a semantic entity alignment.

RQ₇ : In a non-privacy-preserving context, entity alignment can be based on shared personal identifiers, such as name, address, gender, and date of birth, that are effectively used as weak IDs [28]. However, in the privacy preserving scenario weak identifiers are considered private to each party. There is an increasing trend of concerns about privacy of the data that is being collected and/or shared by companies or online websites [19]. These concerns are related to both the consumer, whose information is often used or traded with little consent, and the collector, who is often responsible for protecting the collected data.

RQ₈ : Semantic entity alignment is a developing field with many opportunities for the further research. Recent developments in knowledge graph embeddings is an example of one of the many directions that have been explored continuously over the years [68]. Embedding-based techniques consist of the encoded entities in a continuous embedding space and the computed entity similarities based on the learned embeddings. Most entity alignment approaches show comparable performance and can outperform other approaches when used with a specific type of data.

3.3 Search strategy

The initial search consists of two methods: manual search and automatic search. Manual search is aimed at looking into top tier journals and conferences that address knowledge and data related

processes. The most prominent journals and conferences were chosen based on the (i) area of expertise and (ii) its ranking. Table 1 presents journals and conferences that received a high score (A* or A) on CORE Rankings Portal.

For the automatic search it is important to first define the search query or multiple queries that capture the information need presented in this literature study. This query needs to capture the goals formulated within each of the research questions. The query usually consists of an exact word/phrase match, AND clause, OR clause, NOT clause, etc. The following search query will be used to retrieve the an initial list of primary studies:

("entity alignment" OR "semantic similarity") AND "machine learning" AND ("multi-source" OR "databases" OR "data sources") AND ("active learning" OR "state-of-the-art" OR "federated learning" OR "privacy" or "user experience")

The digital libraries that are used to search for the relevant literature are presented in Table 2. These libraries are chosen based on their reputation among scientific libraries, ease of search and diversity of the literature retrieved from the search query. If for some reason a digital library does not accept the defined keyword query, then a different, much simpler query is used to retrieve a list of studies. The simpler query consists of "entity alignment" AND "semantic" AND "machine learning" keywords. Other queries are also used to retrieve additional results, if the number of results is too low. These other queries contain synonyms of the words present in the original query or additional keywords.

Table 3 presents a number of definitions of the key terms that are used to guide the literature search.

Figure 2 shows the phases of the search protocol used for the Systematic Literature Study. The numbers between the parentheses denote a number of studies retrieve from the search and number of articles left after each phase of the search process.

3.4 Application of Selection Criteria

A part of the search process is the inclusion/exclusion criteria. This step ensures that every selected primary study is of a high quality, which makes it accurate and reliable.

- I1- Studies focusing on using semantics to compute entity similarity. This inclusion criterion is utilized to select exclusively studies considering semantics.
- I2- Studies focusing on the quality metrics for the assessment of the semantic similarity. This inclusion criterion is utilized to filter out studies that do not consider quality evaluation of the given approach.
- I3- Studies presenting or using a technique/approach aimed at facilitating processes within the semantic entity alignment pipeline. With this inclusion criteria, we ensure that only papers discussing techniques that are used in the semantic entity alignment are included.
- I4- Studies that were published within the last 5 years with regard to the time of writing of this systematic literature review. This inclusion criteria ensures recent work in the area of semantic entity alignment which has a better chance at retrieving the best approaches and quality measures developed in this area.

Figure 2: Phases of the search process and the number of primary studies in each phase of SLR.

- I5- Journal papers, conference papers, theses, technical reports, or books that were published in the high CORE ranking sources. This inclusion criteria gives a better chance at finding state-of-the-art work, ignoring research that has less value.
- E1- Studies in the form of editorials and tutorial, short papers, and poster, as they are deemed to not provide the required level of detail and information.
- E2- Studies that have not been published in English, as their analysis would result to be too time consuming.

Source (journals and conferences)	Ranking	Acronym
ACM Computing Surveys	A*	CSUR
ACM International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management	A	CIKM
ACM International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining	A*	KDD
ACM International Conference on Web Search and Data Mining	A*	WSDM
ACM Special Interest Group on Management of Data Conference	A*	SIGMOD
IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering	A*	TKDE
International Conference on Data Engineering	A*	ICDE
International Conference on the Principles of Knowledge Representation and Reasoning	A*	KR

Table 1: Rankings (CORE) of journals and conferences used in the manual search.

Digital Library	Acronym
ACM Digital Library	ACM DL
IEEE Xplore Digital Library	IEEE Xplore
Springer Publishing	Springer
ScienceDirect	ScienceDirect
Web of Science	Web of Science
Elsevier's Scopus	Scopus

Table 2: Digital libraries used in the automatic search.

Term	Definition	References
Machine Learning	A field of computer science that studies algorithms and techniques for automating solutions to complex problems that are hard to program using conventional programming methods.	Rebala et al. [59]
Semantic Similarity	Semantic similarity is the similarity between two classes of objects in a taxonomy.	Lin [42]
Semantic Search Semantic Matching	A novel approach where semantic correspondences are discovered by computing, and returning as a result, the semantic information implicitly or explicitly codified in the labels of nodes and arcs.	Giunchiglia et al. [23]
Entity Alignment	The goal of entity alignment is to take a collection of uncertain entity references (or references, in short) from a single data source or multiple data sources, discover the unique set of underlying entities, and map each reference to its corresponding entity.	Bhattacharya and Getoor [6]
Semantic Knowledge Graph	A system aimed at extracting and representing the knowledge of a domain automatically from a corpus of documents representative of that domain.	Grainger et al. [25]
Search Engine	A search engine is the practical application of information retrieval techniques to large-scale data collections.	Croft et al. [17]
Active Learning	A learning problem or system where the learner has some role in determining on what data it will be trained. This is in contrast to Passive Learning, where the learner is simply presented with a training set over which it has no control.	Cohn [15]
Decentralized computing	Allocation of resources, possibly both hardware and software, to each individual workstation, in contrast to allocating majority of the resources to a centralized location.	Pandl et al. [51]
Data Privacy Preservation	The privacy-preserving aspects and techniques of machine learning cover the family of methods and architectures developed to protect the privacy of people whose data are used by machine learning (ML) algorithms.	Matwin [46]

Table 3: Term definitions and the taxonomy of keywords for query search.

E3- Studies that have not been peer reviewed, in order to ensure the high quality of the studies considered.

E4- Duplicate papers or extensions of already included papers, in order to avoid possible threats to conclusion validity.

E5- Papers that are not available for preview, as we cannot inspect them.

3.5 Search Process

The search process has been carried out according to the steps summarized in Figure 2. It was possible to retrieve a sufficient amount of papers through both manual and automatic search methods.

By manually going through the contents of the selected conferences and journals it was possible to retrieve 912 articles that seemed related to the topic of this literature study. After going through the abstracts and conclusions of the retrieved articles, it was possible to find and filter out a small number of articles, where 890 still made it to the next stage. After that, the inclusion/exclusion criteria described in section 3.4 was applied after which there were only 434 articles remaining. For this step the most effective inclusion criteria was related to the articles being recent enough, so at most five years old. The next step is to perform scanning and skimming of the full articles. After this step only 41 studies made it further into the search process. The next step involves scanning the references of the remaining papers, which increased the number of articles to 55. After fully reading the articles, 49 of them were chosen to progress further to the quality assessment. Table 4 depicts what percentages of primary studies have positive and negative answers to the quality assessment questions. After this step there were 43 high quality papers left as part of the manual search.

The automatic query search through popular digital libraries resulted in 482 articles in total. After the inspection of the abstracts and conclusions, there were 329 articles left. Inclusion/exclusion criteria reduced the number of articles to 277. After scanning and skimming the studies, the number of articles dropped to 19. After inspecting the references of the papers that were considered for snowballing, the number of articles increased to 28. After fully reading the articles three of them were excluded in the process, resulting in 25 articles total. There was only one low quality publication, which means 24 articles were finalized as part of the automatic search.

Finally, 67 high quality primary studies have been chosen to be used as part of this systematic literature study. $\frac{2}{3}$ of the finalized primary studies come from the manual search of the high-rated conferences and journals. The final list of primary studies has been classified in categories based on the type of entity alignment and machine learning used to compute semantic similarity between entities.

3.6 Study Replicability

To ensure its replicability, the steps of the literature study have been documented and the data is made available via Google Spreadsheets¹. This includes: (1) all 1,394 search results with scraped basic information, including title, authors, year and publication place. (2) the selection criteria applied, including a selection argumentation. (3) a small description of each selected paper (4) a classification of the selected papers.

¹https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/11a18Nha4S8IwwfiKNVue0m8lpn93wOMaMc1Njd6wF_o/edit?usp=sharing

4 RESULTS

This section is dedicated to reporting the results categorized by the research questions formulated in this literature study.

4.1 Computing Semantic Similarity Between Entities (RQ1)

From the selected primary studies, nine papers address methods for computing semantic similarity, however, more than twenty studies briefly touch upon this topic as well, without describing the details. The most typical approaches for computing semantic similarity are *distance-based*, *IC-based* or *hybrid*. Hybrid approaches currently achieve the best performance and receive the most attention in the current state of the research. The key differences between these approaches are described in this paragraph.

Most semantic similarity metrics exploit either the semantic information that comes from the structure, such as path length and depth, of the underlying entity knowledge base or the statistical Information Content (IC), which is a way to measure the specificity of the entity concept. High IC values represent more specific entities (e.g. Amsterdam), while low values represent more general entities (e.g. city). Many commonly used semantic similarity approaches (e.g., path [58] or lch [20]) fail to correctly reflect the similarity of two entities that have the same path length, which is known as the uniform distance problem. In their work Zhu and Iglesias [82] propose a method (*wpath*) to measure semantic similarity between real-world entities by combining path length and IC to weight the shortest path length between entities. The difference between corpus-based IC similarity [34] and graph-based IC is that corpus-based IC is derived from the distributions of entities over a textual corpus, which is then used to create annotated entities and combine them into a domain corpus. The disadvantage of this approach is that it has a high computational cost. In knowledge bases, however, the instances are already extracted from the textual corpus and annotated by their representative entities. This allows graph-based IC to compute IC based on the distributions of entities over instances. By using this approach, *wpath* has proven to be one of the best performing metrics in terms of accuracy and F-score.

The *wpath* metric tries to alleviate the uniform distance problem by combining the shortest path with IC, however when the IC decreases, the path contribution increases, which makes it difficult to differentiate between final similarities. To address this problem Alkhamees et al. [2] propose a weighted information-content (*wic*) semantic similarity metric that makes use of the IC of the least common subsumer of two entities that are being compared and the depth information that comes from the knowledge graphs. To combine these two similarity components they propose using calibrated cooperative contributions. When compared to *wpath*, *wic* seems to perform better in terms of accuracy and F-score when there is an entity type imbalance present in the knowledge bases, otherwise *wpath* outperforms *wic*. This is of course highly dependant on the data being used to compute semantic similarity. In reality these two approaches are quite comparable in performance.

However, graph-based approaches are not the type of similarity measure that have been getting recent improvements. For example, a corpus-based approach by Yin et al. [76] uses a combination of explicit semantic similarity information and implicit semantic similarity information to train two models that are used together

Quality assessment question	Yes (%)	No (%)
Does the paper conduct a research or is based on a research?	93.24	6.76
Is the aim of the research clearly stated?	87.84	12.16
Is there a sufficient explanation of the research?	83.78	16.22
Is the research design appropriate to address the aims of the research?	82.43	17.57
Is there a clear statement of findings?	77.03	22.93
Does the study carry a scientific value?	100.00	0.00

Table 4: Quality assessment of the primary studies.

to identify and compute semantic similarity through word embeddings. The similarity between two vectors is approximated by their cosine similarity, then the word embedding models for explicit and implicit information are evaluated by measuring the Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient [18] with the help of human judgment. This is an example of a method that uses semantic information about entities to outperform a number of state-of-the-art approaches that use word embeddings.

4.2 Quality Metrics of Semantic Similarity (RQ2)

Out of the selected primary studies, ten of them describe or propose evaluation methods of measuring semantic similarity. Of course, many other studies makes use of different evaluation methods, however they do not provide the level of detail to classify them under RQ2. The two main approaches are quite similar, which are Spearman’s and Pearson’s correlation coefficients. Other popular approaches involve calculating accuracy, precision, recall or the combination of different metrics (F-score). These quality evaluation metrics are described in more detail in this section.

Quality metrics help us distinguish and quantify the difference between similarity approaches. To evaluate the quality of wpath semantic similarity measure, Zhu and Iglesias [82] adapt Spearman’s correlation measure between similarity scores generated by their method and scores identified by humans. According to Zhu and Iglesias, this is the most established methodology for evaluating semantic similarity measures. Both Spearman’s and Pearson’s correlations coefficients have been commonly used in the recent studies, where the result of both quality metrics are equivalent if rating scores are ordered. To evaluate wpath, Spearman’s correlation coefficient was preferred only for the minor reason of convenience. Alkhamees et al. [2] also report on using Spearman’s coefficient to evaluate the quality of their proposed semantic similarity metric. Higher correlation score indicates better performance of the similarity metric, while lower score means that the result of the similarity metric is inconsistent with respect to human judgements. When comparing multiple similarity measures, it is important to keep in mind that Spearman’s rank correlation coefficients are dependent on the human ratings, hence it is important to conduct statistical significance tests on the dependent correlations. Zhu and Iglesias follow the Steiger’s z-test [66] to calculate statistical significance test between Spearman’s correlation coefficients produced by different semantic similarity methods. This test uses a one-tailed hypothesis test for assessing the difference between two paired correlations. The statistical significance tests determines if there

is a statistical significance in the improvement of the correlation coefficient for each dataset used to test the similarity metrics on.

In a similar way, Pearson’s correlation coefficient can be used to correlate the scores computed by their similarity measure with the judgments provided by humans. Li et al. [39] adapt this quality measure to conduct a quality evaluation of their proposed efficient density adaptive edge weight semantic similarity model. Pearson’s correlation coefficient works by observing whether there is a linear relevance between the measured values and the human judgments, which can be classified as a problem of linear correlation between variables in statistics. The main difference between Spearman’s and Pearson’s correlation is that the first one works with monotonic relationship, while the second one does not.

In addition to the aforementioned quality metrics, many studies [2, 82] also employ other metrics, such as accuracy, precision, recall and F-measure [13] to compare different similarity measures among each other.

4.3 State-of-the-art Machine Learning Approaches in Semantic Entity Alignment Pipeline (RQ3)

The trend of entity alignment research has increased in the past few years. Figure 3 gives an indication of the difference in the number of papers related to entity alignment being published with seventeen hundred papers being published in the year 2000 and almost ten thousand papers in the year 2020.

In this literature review, as much as twenty-nine selected papers focus on proposing, extending or comparing ML-based semantic entity alignment approaches. We identify and describe in more detail seven state-of-the-art approaches in this section. The main similarity of every studied state-of-the-art approach is the use of the embeddings to represent the data in the form of vectors. The learned embeddings are then used to train a machine learning model. Ideally, the goal of the embeddings is to capture some of the semantics of the input data by placing semantically similar inputs close together in the vector space. Different approaches described in this section learn different kinds of embeddings (relation, entity, position, etc) by using different methods (GCN, GNN, pre-trained, etc). The are many differences between the approaches, where the main ones are the kind of information is used to perform entity alignment (relations, neighbors, structure, external ontology, etc) and what kind of machine learning approaches are used (supervised learning, unsupervised, self-supervised, reinforcement, deep). This section gives a short summary of each of the state-of-the-art approaches identified in this study.

Figure 3: The distribution of papers related to entity alignment on ACM digital library.

Some learning models can be trained by using the semantic information of the data, which enhances their ability to identify patterns and find similarities between pairs of entities. One of such approaches is proposed by Zhu et al. [84], which implements the relation-aware neighborhood matching (RNM) model that explores useful information from the connected relations. By giving two knowledge graphs (KGs) and a set of seed alignments of entities as input, it jointly learns the embeddings of entities and relations using graph convolutional networks (GCNs) with a TransE-like [9] regularizer. After that, it iteratively aligns the entities and relations in a semi-supervised manner. In each iteration, it utilizes the graph structure information to determine new matching pairs of entities and relations by combining a relation-aware and an entity-aware neighborhood matching modules.

Another way to learn graph embeddings is to develop a graph neural network (GNN) to obtain an initial ranking of soft correspondences between nodes. This approach is adopted in the study of Fey et al. [21], where they propose a two-stage neural architecture for learning and refining structural correspondences between graphs. After computing GNN-based localized node embeddings, they employ synchronous message passing networks to iteratively re-rank the soft correspondences to reach a matching consensus in local neighborhoods between graphs. They show that their underlying message passing scheme computes a well-founded measure of consensus for corresponding neighborhoods, which is then used to guide the iterative re-ranking process.

Many entity alignment approaches are designed with specific applications in mind. For example, focused on applying entity alignment for decision-making Zeng et al. [79] present a model based on reinforcement learning (CEAFF). By using the reinforcement learning framework, they devise the coherence and exclusiveness constraints to characterize the interdependence and restrict collective alignment. Additionally, to feed more precise inputs to the reinforcement learning model, they employ representative features to capture different aspects of the similarity between entities in heterogeneous KGs, which are integrated by an adaptive feature fusion strategy.

Another embedding-based model (COTSAE) is proposed by Yang et al. [75], where it is proposed to combine the structure and attribute information of entities by co-training two embedding learning components. They also propose a joint attention method for the model to learn the attentions of attribute types and values cooperatively. Tang et al. [69] present an interaction model that focuses on leveraging the semantic information. Instead of aggregating neighbors, they compute the interactions between neighbors which can capture fine-grained matches of neighbors, while also modeling the interactions of attributes.

Existing supervised methods for entity alignment require a training dataset to be provided to them and they focus on pulling each pair of positively labeled entities close to each other. However, the learning of entity alignment can possibly benefit more from pushing sampled (unlabeled) negatives far away than pulling positive aligned pairs close, according to Liu et al. [43]. In their study they present yet another model (SelfKG), a self-learning model that leverages this discovery to design a contrastive learning strategy across two KGs. However, not all entity alignment models require the training data in the first place. A solution proposed by Zeng et al. [78] offers an unsupervised framework that performs entity alignment (UEA) in the open world. Specifically, it first mines useful features from the entity information present within the KGs, such as the attributes, descriptions and classes. Then, it devises an unmatchable entity prediction module to filter out unmatchable entities and produce preliminary alignment results. These preliminary results are regarded as the pseudo-labeled data and forwarded to the progressive learning framework to generate structural representations, which are integrated with the entity information to provide a more comprehensive view for alignment. Finally, the progressive learning framework gradually improves the quality of structural embeddings and enhances the alignment performance by enriching the pseudo-labeled data with alignment results from the previous round. This solution does not require labeled data and succeeds at effectively filtering out unmatchable entities.

4.4 Active Learning in Semantic Entity Alignment Pipeline? (RQ4)

While datasets used for benchmarking usually do contain the ground truth and training data, most real-world datasets do not. In reality, creating alignments that can be used to train a machine learning model is time consuming and often requires human annotators. [5] This is why active learning for semantic entity alignment has received a lot of attention in the recent years. From the selected papers, five of them focus on the use of active and also passive learning methods for the semantic entity alignment. Some papers propose approaches that focus on the labeling stage [5] in the entity alignment pipeline and some focus more on the matching stage [32]. Most recent studies implement deep active learning, however one study describes an approach that uses pre-trained language models. This sections focuses on some of the most prominent approaches in the fields of active learning and semantic entity alignment.

A study done by Jain et al. [32] proposes an entity alignment model (DIAL), which is based on scalable active learning that jointly learns embeddings to maximize recall for blocking and accuracy for matching blocked pairs. They claim that passive learning methods on tasks like entity alignment require large amounts of labeled

data to yield useful models, while active learning is a promising approach in low resource settings.

On the contrary, Berrendorf et al. [5] claim that by testing different active and passive learning strategies, they could conclude that passive learning approaches, which can be efficiently precomputed and deployed, achieve comparable performance to the active learning strategies.

Many other semantic entity alignment approaches have been reported to use active learning within its entity alignment pipeline. Bogatu et al. [8] use active learning to reduce the cost of labeling training data through an approach that builds on the properties conferred by the use of deep autoencoders. Li et al. [40] integrate active learning into their method of entity similarity calculation for knowledge graphs. Kasai et al. [36] implement a low-resource deep entity alignment model with transfer and active Learning. Loster et al. [44] use active learning to construct deep Siamese neural networks, capable of learning a similarity measure that is tailored to the characteristics of a particular dataset. Nafa et al. [48] propose an active deep learning model of risk sampling for entity alignment. Risk sampling aims at sampling challenging examples for the classifier and produce better representation learning by looking farther than the low confidence regions in the current representation space. Finally, Qian et al. [57] propose an active learning model for large-scale entity alignment, which learns, multiple rules each having significant coverage of the space of entity matches. An interesting direction for the research in active learning is to find a good way to integrate transfer learning, which will allow to reuse the labels provided by the users and reduce the amount of required labels for the future models.

4.5 Optimizing User Experience for ML-Based Semantic Entity Alignment (RQ5)

In the context of this study, user experience is evaluated with regard to the specific applications which deploy machine learning models to perform semantic entity alignment. Twelve of the selected studies focus on optimizing user experience as part of the discussed entity alignment methods. It is possible to improve the scalability of the entity alignment algorithms by adopting graph neural networks as described in [83], while adopting graph attention networks enables improvements in personalized recommendations as described in [67]. The remains of this section focus on the applications of entity alignment, where user experience plays an important role.

A great example of user-focused entity alignment is the study by Sun et al. [67] on personalized recommender systems. Recommender systems often suffer from data sparsity and cold start problems, which is why Sun et al. propose using visual knowledge graphs for alignment and recommendations by leveraging valuable semantic knowledge as auxiliary information. In their study they propose a Multi-modal Knowledge Graph Attention Network (MK-GAT) to better enhance recommender systems by leveraging different types of the textual and visual knowledge available. Specifically, they describe a multi-modal graph attention technique to conduct information propagation over multi-modal knowledge graphs, and then use the resulting aggregated embedding representation to improve quality of the recommendations and user experience.

Another way improve user experience is to introduce the construction and alignment of knowledge graphs for social networks.

This has been done by He et al. [30], where they propose a deep and holistic approach, which improves the user experience and powers the products around the social network. In social networks a common issue is the making connections between data that comes from different languages. Chen et al. [12] aim at optimizing user experience in their model that addresses language gaps in cross-language applications that implement multilingual knowledge graphs. In their paper they discuss how aligning entities in multilingual KGs has recently attracted an increasing amount of research attention and is widely known as the problem of cross-lingual entity alignment.

With scalability in mind, which is another important factor of user experience, Zhu et al. [83] propose a novel collective aggregation function that (1) relieves the incompleteness of knowledge graphs via both cross-graph and self attentions, (2) scales up efficiently with mini-batch training paradigm and effective neighborhood sampling strategy. Scalability has also been addressed in a study by Moretti et al. [47]. It focuses on web applications and concludes that an upgrade in scalability can improve user experience because a user does not have wait as long for the system to react to their requests and the system does not continuously refresh or change the produced results.

4.6 Semantic Entity Alignment in a decentralized environment? (RQ6)

A decentralized environment poses its unique challenges to the existing entity alignment methods. Since the data may come in a distributed way from multiple data sources, matching parts of it requires specific techniques to make the whole process as fast and accurate as possible. From the selected primary studies, six of them touch upon the implementation of entity alignment in a decentralized environment. There have been recent implementations in the medical entity alignment with regard to a decentralized environment. The difference in approaches rely on the type of data stored in the system. Both textual and graph embeddings are used for the medical entity alignment. Another rising phenomena in a decentralized entity alignment is the use of generative adversarial nets. This section further describes how some studies implement their entity alignment techniques in a decentralized environment.

Peng et al. [55] propose a novel decentralized scalable learning framework named Federated Knowledge Graphs Embedding (FKGE), where embeddings from different knowledge graphs can be learnt in an asynchronous and peer-to-peer manner while preserving the privacy of the underlying data. The framework first makes use of the semantic knowledge present in the KGs to learn the embeddings. FKGE exploits adversarial generation between pairs of KGs to semantically search and translate identical entities and relations of different domains into near embedding spaces. These embeddings are suitable to perform entity alignment between entities present in multiple KGs.

There have also been recent developments in the pharmaceutical field related to distributed semantic similarity computations of knowledge graph entities. Abdelaziz et al. [1] propose a semantic prediction framework for drug-drug interactions in which various sources of drug-related data and knowledge are used as inputs and give predictions as outputs using a logistic regression classifier. The process starts with semantic integration of data into a knowledge base describing drug attributes and relationships with various

related entities such as enzymes, chemical structures, and pathways. The KG is then used to compute several similarity measures between the drugs in a scalable and distributed framework.

4.7 Privacy-preserving Semantic Entity Alignment (RQ7)

In total, there are five selected primary studies that focus on privacy preservation during the semantic entity alignment. However, the approaches described in those papers have different applications. For example, Peng et al. [55] focus on the data that comes from multiple sources and how it affects the privacy of that data. Additionally, Zhang et al. [80] present the dangers to privacy during the semantic social network entity alignment, which deals with user-sensitive data. The rest of this section describes in more detail how privacy is treated and what are the dangers to privacy during the semantic entity alignment.

The decentralized environment can pose some serious privacy related issues, where some nodes in the system do have access to certain private information and some do not. This is why the federated knowledge graph embedding framework proposed by Peng et al. [55] also addresses privacy preservation in its implementation. Given two KGs with aligned entities and relations, FKGE exploits a Generative Adversarial Net (GAN) [24] structure to unify the embeddings of aligned entities and relations. This idea originates from MUSE [16] which uses a translational mapping matrix in the generator to align two manifolds in the GAN's intermediate vector space. After GAN training, the synthesized embeddings are able to learn features from both KGs and therefore can replace original embeddings as refined and unified embeddings. It is sufficient for GAN training that only the generated outputs and gradients are transmitted without revealing raw data. However, even for generated embeddings, there are still privacy concerns for reconstruction attacks. It is possible that neural models may memorize inputs and reconstruct inputs from corresponding outputs [10]. To further address the privacy issue, they introduce differential privacy to privatize generated embeddings. Differential privacy provides a strong guarantee for protecting any single embedding in the generator outputs since inclusion and exclusion of a particular embedding will not affect the outcome distribution too much.

Privacy is a known risk of applying entity alignment techniques, especially for the task of account linking across social networks [80], in which certain user identity data is important toward performing alignment. Recent research papers on differential privacy [22, 81] and privacy-preserving graph analytics [29, 38] have shown promising results toward privacy protection. The combination of these techniques and entity alignment could offer an opportunity to generate high-quality alignment while protecting sensitive information about individuals.

4.8 Research Directions for ML-based Semantic Entity Alignment (RQ8)

From the study of Pei et al. [54] about graph neural networks for cross-lingual entity alignment between knowledge graphs, it is clear that their model can be improved by finding a reliable way to reduce human effort in creating a set of trusted entity pairs as the positive samples. Moreover, their graph neural network approach misrecognise some labeled real entity pairs as noisy pairs and some noisy entity pairs as real pairs, which means more work

could be done to reduce the effect of misrecognized entity pairs on the performance of entity alignment. Finally, it is also possible to expand the exploration and discussion about noise in the attribute of entities and knowledge graphs.

With respect to reinforcement learning for entity alignment [79] it is possible to research more advanced feature encoders that can better exploit available features for alignment. In addition, it is worth exploring collective alignment algorithms that can further mitigate the error propagation caused by the wrong matches.

5 DISCUSSION

The most important findings of this systematic literature review are summarized in Table 5 and the landscape² of ML-based semantic entity alignment is visualized in Figure 4. The landscape figure organizes the findings of this literature study by the research question it belongs to. In addition, Figure 5 depicts a swimlane-like diagram representing different workflow pipelines used by different state-of-the-art ML-based semantic entity alignment approaches. This diagram should serve as a guidance tool for all researchers interested in ML-based semantic entity alignment or related fields. Finally, Table 6 contains the summary of a number of features of different state-of-the-art semantic entity alignment approaches.

²Created using a tool named Coggle: <https://coggle.it/>

RQs	Method name	Method description
Compute semantic similarity among entities.	wpath	Combines structure of the knowledge graph and the information content (IC) [82].
	wic	Implements calibrated cooperative contributions of IC and the depth information [2].
Quality metrics to assess a semantic similarity.	Spearman's and Pearson's correlations coefficients.	Correlations measure how close each semantic metric prediction was to human judgement [2].
	Accuracy, precision, recall and F-measure.	Measures used in the information retrieval domain to measure how well an information retrieval system retrieves the relevant information requested by a user [70].
State-of-the-art ML approaches in semantic entity alignment pipeline.	RNM	Semi-supervised relation-aware model that utilizes neighborhood matching [84].
	CEAFF	Reinforcement learning-based model with adaptive features [79].
	DGMC	Deep learning entity alignment based on graph neural networks [21].
	COTSAE	Combining structure and attribute information of entities by co-training two embedding learning models [75].
	BERT-INT	Deep learning based interaction model [69].
	SelfKG	Self-learning model that uses pre-trained language models and neighborhood aggregators [43].
	UEA	Unsupervised learning model that mines useful feature, filters out unmatchable entities to create preliminary alignment and more [78].
Active learning in semantic entity alignment pipeline.	DIAL	Scalable active learning model that learns graph embeddings [32].
	-	Active learning using approximate vertex cover algorithm [5, 56].
Optimizing user experience in semantic entity alignment using machine learning.	MKGAT	Recommendations based on knowledge graph entity alignment [67].
	-	Deep and holistic entity alignment for social knowledge graph [30].
	CG-MuAlign	Mini-batch training paradigm and effective neighborhood sampling strategy for scalability [83].
Semantic entity alignment in a decentralized environment.	FKGE	Federated knowledge graph embeddings [55].
	Tiresias	Semantic prediction framework for drug-drug interactions [1].
Preserving privacy during semantic entity alignment.	FKGE	Privacy-preserving model based on Generative Adversarial Nets [55].
	ALLEN	Privacy-preserving account linking across social networks [80].
Research directions in ML-based semantic entity alignment field.	-	Improve graph neural networks by eliminating human effort in creating a set of trusted entity pairs [54].
	-	Reduce the effect of misrecognized entity pairs on the performance of entity alignment [54].
	-	Expand the exploration and discussion about noise in the attribute of entities and knowledge graphs [54].
	-	Advanced feature encoders for reinforcement learning-based entity alignment [79].

Table 5: Overview of the systematic literature study results.

Figure 4: The landscape of the ML-based semantic entity alignment.

Figure 5: A swimlane-like diagram that depicts workflow pipelines of different state-of-the-art entity alignment approaches.

Features	Approaches											
	RNM	CEAFF	DGMC	COTSAAE	BERT-INT	SelfKG	UEA	DIAL	CG-MuAlign	FKGE	Tiresias	ALLEN
Supports textual data entity alignment (EA)	✓	✓		✓			✓				✓	✓
Supports graph data EA	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓
Makes use of pre-trained models for EA	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓						
Contains evaluation of the proposed approach for EA	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Makes use of benchmarking datasets	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Supports large-scale data		✓	✓	✓		✓		✓	✓	✓		
Describes existing tools that implement this approach			✓					✓				
Contains comparison to other EA approaches	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓

Table 6: The summary of features of different entity alignment approaches.

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6 THREATS TO VALIDITY

This section identifies a number of threats to the internal and external validity of this study.

6.1 External validity

In this study the main external threat to validity may come from the primary studies not being representative of the whole research on machine learning-based semantic entity alignment. In order to mitigate such risk, a search strategy has been employed that includes both automatic and manual searches. Furthermore, in this study only peer-reviewed papers were considered and any other work is excluded. We do not foresee this criterion to have impacted this study as the considered papers need to have undergone a rigorous peer-review process, which is an established requirement for quality publications. Lastly, a well defined inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied.

6.2 Internal validity

The threats to internal validity target the design and execution of the systematic literature review. To prevent possible design errors, the systematic literature review protocol has been followed, which is summarized in Section 3. In addition, the inclusion/exclusion criteria used to select the primary studies was designed and reviewed by multiple people.

6.3 Construct validity

The threats to construct validity target the alignment between the research question and the measurements of the review. We evaluate the effectiveness of our search query with a list of pilot studies that has proven to answer the research query based on the additional checks and validations of the experts in the field.

6.4 Conclusion validity

The threats to conclusion validity come from the the data extraction process not being reproducible. For this study each data extraction step has been recorded in detail and we could reproduce all the steps successfully and get the same data.

7 CONCLUSION

ML-based semantic entity alignment is a trending research field with many recent studies published in highly ranked journals and conferences. Entity alignment aims at linking data that comes from different data sources based on their similarity. In this study we focus on semantic similarity measures only that allows us to learn the meaning of entities in different knowledge graphs before aligning them among each other.

This study conducts a systematic literature review to give an overview of the most recent studies in the field of entity alignment, as well as answer some of the research questions that are formulated based on the current research trends in the field. Eight research question are considered when constructing search queries used to explore research studies published in some of the highly ranked journals and conferences and to retrieve 1,394 research studies. After going through the phases of the search and applying

inclusion/exclusion criteria 67 primary studies have been selected to answer the research questions from this study.

The main findings of this study have been summarized into a table overview (Table 5) and a visual taxonomy (Figure 4). Some of the most recent and best performing semantic similarity methods are wpath and wic. To analyze the quality of semantic similarity most recent studies utilize Spearman’s or Pearson’s correlation coefficients. Many state-of-the-art approaches have been proposed recently, where some of the most notable are based on deep learning, reinforcement learning, self-supervised learning and unsupervised learning. Many active learning solutions have been proposed that aim at improving accuracy of the final model. Many recent studies also touch upon user experience, privacy preservation, decentralized environment and other properties related to entity alignment.

For future work it is possible to extend this study by including entity alignment models that do not make use of semantic information, but rather topological data, string similarities, knowledge extraction, different types of graph neural networks and more. Another direction for future work is to explore different application of ML-based semantic entity alignment, for example in semantic search engines, recommender systems, document alignment, applications in pharmaceutical and biomedical sciences and more.

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